

The Role and Significance of Digital Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

Digital Entrepreneurship is a well-established concept. However, recent progresses in the context of digital entrepreneurship call for revision and advancement. Digital entrepreneurship is largely defined as creating new ventures and transforming existing businesses by digital technologies

The numerous possible combinations of technology and entrepreneurship have resulted in a multiplicity of phenomena with different characteristics. This article is focused on the identification and description of digital entrepreneurship in times of digitization. Based on present examples, we identify and describe classifications of digital entrepreneurship, digital technology entrepreneurship, and digital entrepreneurship. With this new description of terms, we would like to encourage discussion between researchers, digital entrepreneurs, and the impact of technology on entrepreneurship, and set a future research agenda. Innovation and digital entrepreneurship are set forward a view where entrepreneurship, achieved either by individual persons or large firms, is perceived as the driving force of innovation. Entrepreneurial activity spins around the identification and exploitation of opportunities in order to generate value and capture a considerable share of that value. Over the last years an increasing discourse on digital innovation has developed, while the digital entrepreneur has been more infrequently addressed. In this conceptual paper, we discuss the nature of digital entrepreneurship based on a theoretical framework entrenched in the discourse on digital innovation and the characteristics of digital things. We contend that it makes more sense to talk about entrepreneurship in a digital society, than the digital entrepreneur as a new species. By spread over the framework on examples, we discuss different key dimensions of entrepreneurship

Keywords: Digital Entrepreneurship, Digital Innovation, Technology Entrepreneurship.

Introduction

Innovation and entrepreneurship always goes hand in hand. The entrepreneurship, performed by individual entrepreneurs or large firms, was the powerful force for innovation and growth (Schumpeter 1911/1934). In the era of the digitalization of society, a increasing discourse on digital innovation is emerging (Yoo et al. 2011; 2013), while digital entrepreneurship has been more infrequently addressed. A change of determinations to conceptualize entrepreneurship in the connection of technology and entrepreneurship has occurred, with associated concepts such as digital entrepreneurship (Bouwman and

Hulsink 2003), Internet entrepreneurship (McKelvey 2002; Millman et al. 2011; Colombo and Delmastro 2002), and E-commerce entrepreneurship (Sebora et al. 2009). While, these papers acknowledge the technology as a transformative power and source of opportunities, they do not link the specific features of digitality to entrepreneurship. While knowing digital entrepreneurship, very little theorizing is spent on the nature of digitality itself (Nambisan 2017).

In this conceptual paper, we focus on the nature of digital entrepreneurship based on a theoretical framework engrained in the discourse on digital innovation and the features of digital artefacts. We claim that it makes more sense to talk about entrepreneurship in the digital society, than the digital entrepreneur as a new species. The research question that sets out to guide this article is: How do the unique features of digital technology and the digitalization of society affect entrepreneurship?

The paper continues as follows. The next section provides an overview of entrepreneurship theory. We then position the paper within related research in the connection of entrepreneurship and information systems. Following that, we present a framework for digital entrepreneurship rooted in digital innovation and characteristics of digital artefacts. The subsequent section discusses examples of digital entrepreneurship in relation to the framework. The last section concludes the paper.

Entrepreneurship Theory

Here we will discuss on some of the main theoretical problems in entrepreneurship research. Given all facets of entrepreneurship occurring in this literature, we focus on the core of the classical entrepreneurship literature and on dimensions that we consider most useful for discussing digital entrepreneurship.

Many definitions of entrepreneurial activity revolve around the identification and exploitation of opportunities in order to create value and capture a substantial share of that value. Closely related to this definition are the notions of risk and uncertainty. Schumpeter (1911/1934) defined the entrepreneur as the person who carries out new combinations that causes discontinuity, and thus acts as a leader and contributor to the process of creative destruction. Kirzner (1985) viewed the entrepreneur as someone who perceives profit opportunities and act in order to fill unsatisfied needs in the market or to improve inefficiency. Schumpeter (1942) later viewed entrepreneurship as less individualistic, so that the entrepreneur doesn't have to be a person, but a group of people or an organization.

In the following we present four recurrent themes, that we consider useful for discussing digital entrepreneurship: the nature of opportunities, personal traits of the entrepreneur, risk and uncertainty, and the kind of entrepreneurial engagement.

Literature Review

The purpose of conducting research in the area of technology or digital marketing is because it seems enormous and intimidating. Businesses are looking for perfect picture to start but unaware where and how to start doing digital marketing. Presently, many social media channels such as Google, Facebook, Twitter etc., firms have successfully transformed the attitudes and perceptions of consumers and in the end facilitated revolutionized many businesses. This was done through measurable enormous network of customers with reliable data with real-time feedback of customer involvements.

It is much more convenient for businesses to conduct surveys online with a purpose to get applicable information from targeted groups and analysing the outcome based on their responses. Prospective customers can look for reviews and recommendations to make informed decisions about buying a product or using the service. On the other hand, businesses can use the implementation

strategy to take action on relevant feedback from customers in meeting their needs more effectively and accurately.

Marketing has been there for a long time. Business holders sensed the need to spread the word about their products or services through newspapers and word of mouth. Digital marketing on the other side is becoming popular because it operates mass media devices like television, radio and the Internet. The most common digital marketing tool used today is Search Engine Optimization (SEO). Digital marketing concept initiated from the Internet and search engines ranking of websites.

When the Internet booms in 2001, market was conquered by Google and Yahoo for search optimization. Internet search traffic grew in 2006; the growth of search engine optimization grew for major companies like Google (Smyth 2007). In 2007, the usage of mobile devices enlarged the Internet usage on the move drastically and people all over the world started connecting with each other more conveniently through social media.

In the advanced world, companies have realized the significance of digital marketing. For any businesses to be successful traditional methods for meeting the needs of customers more precisely (Parsons, Zeisser, Waitman 1996).

With many accessibility of so many choices for customers, it is difficult for marketers to create brands and increase traffic for their products and services. Online marketing is a powerful marketing tool for building brands and increasing traffic for companies to achieve success (Song, 2001). Building results and measuring success for advertisement amount spent, digital marketing is more cost-efficient for evaluating ROI on advertisement (Pepelnjak, 2008).

Today marketing techniques have given way to digital marketing. In addition, it is so influential that it can help recover the economy and can create remarkable opportunities for governments to function in a more efficient manner (Munshi, 2012). Singapore firms have experienced the success of digital marketing tools as being effective and useful for achieving results. (Teo, 2005). The growth in digital marketing has been due to the speedy advances in technologies and changing market dynamics (Mort, Sullivan, Drennan, Judy, 2002).

Facebook has opened the door for businesses to communicate with millions of people about products and services and has opened new marketing openings in the market. Marketing professional must firmly understand online social marketing campaigns. The market dynamics all over the world are changing in relation to the young customer’s accessibility to social media and usage. It is so important that strategic integration approaches are embraced in organization’s marketing communication plan (Rohm & Hanna, 2011).

Website Blogs as a best instrument for digital marketing have successfully created an impact for increase in sales revenue, particularly for products where customers can read reviews and write comments about personal experiences. For any type of businesses, online reviews have worked really well as part of their overall strategic marketing strategy (Zhang, 2013). Online service tools are influencing than traditional methods of communication (Helm, Möller, Mauroner, Conrad, 2013). The Internet is the powerful tool for businesses (Yannopoulos, 2011).

Digital Entrepreneurship: A Conceptual Framework

Conventionally, entrepreneurship and innovation have presupposed stable and limited boundaries for new product ideas that underlie an entrepreneurial opening. But regarding digital innovation these restrictions appear instead as fluid and porous; the idea of generativity points to the fact that digital products continue to evolve even after the commercial introduction (Nambisan 2016). An Operating System is continuously in the making, both when it comes to stabilization as well as addition of new landscapes.

Introduce a conceptual model where critical aspect of digital innovation is presented: Here we discuss what types of skills and/or prerequisites are needed to be able to undertake entrepreneurial opportunities in the digital territory.

Digital Products are programmable as well as re-programmable. This fact is fundamental for the emergence of the generative matrix and a software provides almost unlimited flexibility in information manipulation. The entrepreneur can, by employing programming skills, create or alter digital products so that they appear in new ways. This possibility to modifies and use capabilities and affordances which appear within digital products lays the foundation for generatively to emerge. An entrepreneur can both discover as well as a create opportunities with respect to the programmable features.

Digital Products can be editable (Kallinikos et al. 2013). Editability is a built-in property which gives the entrepreneur a chance to create and update content (blogs, vlogs). Any entrepreneur can make use of widespread platforms to tap into already existing user bases. While this possibility lowers the barrier of distributing content on a wider scale – compared to what has traditionally been the case – the notion of the long tail can make the battle for attention from the user base quite a challenge (Anderson 2004). Of course, it can be discussed whether the entrepreneur is a creator, in the sense of creating content. But since this article focuses on digital entrepreneurial logics, it is more important to notice that the entrepreneur must discover a digital opportunity (that is editable) before s/he can create content.

Digital Products are interactive (Kallinikos et al. 2013). Entrepreneurs can make use of digital artefacts by interacting with the functions and affordances they present. By employing digital technologies to facilitate their day-to-day work, entrepreneurs can make their processes more efficient as well as reduce operational costs (Accenture 2014). Maybe this notion of interactivity, more than any of the other, underlines the dilemma of reframing an entrepreneur as a digital one. Because in many cases, entrepreneurs conduct their core business in the tangible world, while all other activities are performed within the digital sphere. Hence, the entrepreneur must cope with both the digital as the non-digital.

Entrepreneurship in the Digital Society

By starting off in the digital territory the entrepreneur appears in a global context from day one. New technologies with new markets as well as reduce the cost of international expansion. Due to the generative, elastic and inexpensive nature of cloud computing, the entrepreneur can act with a great amount of flexibility both when it comes to day -to-day operational activities as well as further development (Zysman and Kenney 2018; Accenture 2014). But on the other hand, the notion of convergence brings entrepreneurs together, operating in the same channel which increases the possibility of rivalry and competition over attention and relevance amongst customer. This might lead to winner-take-all tendencies and a fiercer competition that might be the case for a traditional entrepreneur (Parker, van Alstyne and Choudray 2016; Kenney and Zysman 2016).

Although digital technology lower barriers, the entrepreneur might also face issues quite unique to the digital realm. Consider data as a commodity. Rules and law handing this commodity are not conforming to a global standard. Given that today’s data-driven world presupposes a transparent flow of data, traditionally regulatory approaches are being challenged (Accenture 2014). While in the tangible world, national borders are distinct and well-defined, things are a bit fuzzier in the digital realm.

Digital businesses can appear as immature and not yet stable where policymakers and institutions are trying to catch up. But this stance can be a bit misleading, since latent within such reasoning lies the perceiving of technology as static. But the notion of generatively tells us that technology is all but static, and we do not really know how the future unfolds. With the notion of technology in constant flux follows a view of the world where laws and regulations always will be challenged.

Figure Digital Entrepreneurship Framework

Implications for Digital Entrepreneurship

The digital revolution of most of the input technologies that entrepreneurs use to recommend their innovative ventures of technology entrepreneurs we are able to observe rather than proposing a clear-cut link between digital and technology entrepreneurship, we provide to explain the amendment in that means of “technology” as a time between the extremes drawn by the exploitation of the newest scientific innovations and also the latest application for smartphones.

The construct of digital technology entrepreneurship definitely combines components of technology and digital entrepreneurship. Hence, we tend to propose to counterpoint Bailetti’s(2013) definition of technology entrepreneurship to incorporate specific aspects associated with this explicit variety of entrepreneurship, digital technology entrepreneurship is targeted on the identification and exploitation of opportunities supported scientific or technological data through the formation of digital artefacts. Digital entrepreneurs build companies supported technologies on the one hand, and on services on the opposite hand.

Digital technology entrepreneurs don’t relying solely on associate innovation system as digital entrepreneurs do. They strategically merge technological product data (“technology push”) with shopper ability (“market pull”). However why introduce these terms – area unit there not already enough definitions within the space of entrepreneurship, as mentioned earlier? From an instructional perspective and researchers might use the various classifications of entrepreneurship to be told additional concerning the non-public motivations of entrepreneurs and their start behaviours, funding preferences, etc. One could any argue that such labels may not be relevant to the entrepreneurs themselves. However, we tend to believe that, once it involves entrepreneurs aiming to begin a business, it’d facilitate them to create an aware call on what kind of technology enterpriser they need to be.

Figure Conceptual Representation of a new type of Technology Entrepreneurship: Digital Technology Entrepreneurship

Digital Opportunities

Digital technology appears to change, or add to the behavior on however opportunities arise. The generative potential of digital technology acts as parcel for future innovation to happen. Generatively therefore brings an extra dimension to the connection between enterpriser and chance. Not solely will a chance be created or discovered (Alvarez and Barney 2007), however it may also be enabled. Within the case of discovering and making a chance, the enterpriser actively performs actions to explore and exploit same chance. The intention of the enterpriser is to supply a brand new service or product and convey it to the market. However once it involves describing a chance as enabled, we tend to should contemplate the character of digital technologies as on purpose unfinished (Kallinikos et. al 2013); that Associate in Nursing enterpriser deliberately lets elements of his creation open up for others to use or rest on. From an enterpriser will, within the digital realm, each explore and exploit opportunities (discover/create) still as alter for opportunities to look (enable).

When Associate in Nursing enterpriser permits a chance, s/he cannot recognize in beforehand however this chance are going to be used, or for that matter, if it ever are going to be exploited. For instance, Google Cloud, AWS (Amazon net Services), and Microsoft Azure area unit digital platforms WHO presents innumerable opportunities which may be used for innovation; the services offered, spans from building and managing IT-infrastructures, to information analytics and machine learning services. What these actors do is that they permit opportunities that successively are used as building blocks for innovation by alternative entrepreneurs. Thanks to the self-referential nature of digital technology, the entrepreneurs will themselves successively leave their creation on purpose unfinished for others to make upon. During this method, entrepreneurs recursively modify opportunities that successively ends up in the stratified matter structure of digital technology, wherever platforms area unit engineered upon platforms. Not like creation or discovery of a chance - wherever profits in an exceedingly sense area unit collected directly - the gain of facultative a chance is buried within the future, beside the approaching entrepreneurs’ risk to take advantage of it. a bit like within the case of creation, facultative opportunities is closely associated with uncertainty, since data of future actions is unknown.

If we tend to then come back to the abstract framework earlier conferred, and to it add the discussion regarding opportunities, a visual percept on entrepreneurship within the digital society slowly emerges. wherever the digital artefacts totally different characteristics and relations describes that choices, Associate in Nursing enterpriser will utilize and use to create use of the same artefact and to additional introduce. And wherever the various views on opportunities offers the likelihood for the enterpriser to decide on whether or not s/he can exploit (discover/create) opportunities or modify them – or even each. These decisions can have an effect on the strategic approach. for instance, if Associate in Nursing enterpriser chooses to primarily modify opportunities – to devote to price creation – the strategic decisions are going to be regarding platform thinking and the way to make healthy and vivacious ecosystems.

Personal Traits and Knowledge

What variety of data should associate conventional conquer to be ready to pursue entrepreneurial opportunities within the digital territory? The literature that describes digital entrepreneurs’ characteristics, investigated traits like locus of management, risk -taking propensity, instructional background, previous expertise etcetera. (Sebora et al. 2009; Hull et al. 2007; Colombo and Delmastro 2001; Serarols-Tarrés et al. 2006; Millman et al. 2010). Nothing of what very can be aforementioned to be distinctive for associate bourgeois within the digital realm. Millman et al. (2010) found a correlation between IT-education and temperament to interact in digital

entrepreneurship. This, one may claim, has one thing to try and do with medical aid within the sense that data Technology is that the propulsion behind the method in and of itself. However it's conjointly – and for the bourgeois concept's sake additional significantly – to try and do with data. Somebody that somebody} gains (IT) data and someone don't. That somebody supported conquered data and purchased skills, will discover and seize opportunities wherever others cannot (cf carver et al. 2005; Bull and Willard 1993). From a data perspective, there's no distinction between the digital bourgeois and a conventional bourgeois. It's all concerning gaining adequate data.

If we have a tendency to communicate the abstract framework, we will note that digital artefacts may be approached otherwise. And betting on the approach, the data required to master that approach may take issue. Take the characteristic programmable: To be ready to master this characteristic the bourgeois (or a colleague) should possess the talent of programming. However, the requirement for the extent of competency could vary: On the one hand, to be ready to produce a fancy and innovative physical object, a high level of understanding at intervals of programming is maybe required (e.g. platforms like Uber, Facebook, and Instagram). On the opposite hand, if the bourgeois goes for a combinatorial approach – combining a try of API:s exposed by totally different artefacts - there would possibly exists scenario were simply a rudimentary data of programming is nice enough (cf Fultz 2011). If we have a tendency to then take the characteristics of interactive, the bourgeois is additional a user of existing artefacts that s/he should learn to use: Let or not it's an internet CRM system (Microsoft Dynamics 365; Salesforce) or associate app in a very itinerant (Uber, Whatsapp, FB Messenger), or for that matter, associate OS (Linux, Android, MacOS).

Entrepreneurship within the digital landscape spans wide areas. This ends up in lower barriers for entrance to markets and a colossal range of opportunities to explore. However at constant time, it conjointly needs that adequate data and knowledge exists for having the ability to use these opportunities. Therefore, in terms of data, it's arduous to purpose to a selected kind that's relevant for a digital bourgeois. What is more, it's even tougher to predict what variety of data is desired within the future, since it's troublesome to anticipate on that ways technology unfolds; that of today's techniques and applications that prevails, and which is able to be out-dated.

Conclusion

This paper commenced to theorize digital entrepreneurship and discuss however the characteristics of digital technology and medical aid have an effect on entrepreneurship. We have a tendency to gift a framework for digital entrepreneurship supported the characteristics of digital artefacts and digital innovation. By applying the framework on examples, we have a affinity to discuss four key dimensions of entrepreneurship – the character of opportunities, personal traits of the bourgeois, risk and uncertainty, and replicative or innovative entrepreneurship. We have a tendency to contribute by problematizing digital entrepreneurship in regard to these dimensions. Discovery versus creation theory we have a leaning to add a 3rd component: opportunity facultative that is closely connected to generativist.

We conclude that that digital entrepreneurship in certain fields may require technical knowledge (especially for innovative entrepreneurs), but that the development of digital platforms on the other hand lower these requirements. Finally, many of these platforms are examples of innovative entrepreneurship, in that they both may create or enable opportunities for other entrepreneurs (if they have high generative capacity) and create simpler opportunities to be discovered by self-employed replicative entrepreneurs.

For future research, we suggest investigating whether more dimensions of the framework would be relevant. One example is the nature of individual entrepreneurship as opposed to organizational

entrepreneurship. We also propose that more illustrations of emergent digital phenomena are investigated in relation to entrepreneurship in a digital of society.

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